

CONDUCTED EMISSION MODELS FOR SWITCHING POWER SUPPLIES

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ABSTRACT

Military Standard 461C specifies the limit for harmonic currents generated by electronic equipments in the frequency ranges that cover CE01 emissions (60 Hz - 20 kHz) and CE03 emissions (20 kHz - 50 MHz). These emissions are typical of the electromagnetic interference generated by switching power supplies. A computer model has been developed to study the effect of nonlinear loads on military power distribution systems. Harmonic distortion caused by nonlinear loads is modeled by ideal current sources shunting the appropriate load impedance. The current sources can be given assumed harmonic structures that match measured data. Harmonic voltages and currents are computed at various points in the power distribution system, and the total harmonic distortion is estimated as a figure of merit for the particular configuration. Predicted values of total harmonic distortion will be compared to actual shipboard measurements.

INTRODUCTION

In the past few years much emphasis has been placed on the effects of nonlinear loads on military power distribution systems. Power converters, particularly switching regulators, introduce harmonic currents onto the power distribution system. Harmonic currents introduce many problems including interference with other electronic systems, increased power losses in motors and other magnetic devices, development of secondary harmonic torques that can lead to undesirable machine vibrations, and increased structure currents that flow through input-to-ground capacitors to the ship's ground plane. These harmonic emissions fall into two frequency ranges: 60 Hz - 20 kHz (CE01 emissions) and 20 kHz - 50 MHz (CE03 emissions)[¹]. CE01 emissions are usually related to the rectifier and input smoothing filter, and CE03 emissions are related to the actual switching frequency used in the dc-dc converter. Because many engineers include switching power supplies in their designs, much concern has been expressed about the electromagnetic interference (EMI) caused by these devices on the power distribution systems. Figure 1 shows the harmonic distortion on a laboratory power distribution system. A worst-case computer model has been developed to assess the impact of this EMI on a typical military power distribution system.

Several off-the-shelf power supplies were measured to determine the effects of various types of smoothing filters. Typical switching power supplies use capacitive smoothing filters. These give reasonably good ripple for low cost, weight, and volume. Unfortunately, capacitive smoothing filters become increasingly ineffective at lower frequencies permitting increased harmonic levels to return to the generator and are usually responsible for CE01 emissions failure. Figure 2 shows the spectrum of a three-phase power supply that uses a capacitive type smoothing filter. This spectrum appears flat to some point (the 13th harmonic) and then falls off at $1/n^3$. Several other power supplies were measured and found to have fall-off rates between $1/n$ and $1/n^3$.

Switching power supplies also exhibit conducted emissions in the 20 kHz to 50 MHz range. Designers have typically chosen switching frequencies around 20

kHz because frequencies less than 20 kHz can cause EMI in equipments and are more difficult to filter. Frequencies above 40 kHz can cause additional EMI problems but are easier to filter.

Figure 1. Harmonic Distortion on 60-Hz, Single-Phase Laboratory Powerline

Figure 2. Line Current Spectrum for Phase A of the BQQ-5 Type 4B Power Supply

Some manufacturers are producing 100 Watt switching power supplies that operate at 200 kHz, but the conducted emissions from supplies in this range are highly dependent upon the filtering provided by the manufacturer. In this study, rather than providing a detailed model for every power supply, a general worst-case switching model has been developed. It is assumed that the filter between the rectifier and the switching circuit has been optimized to provide smoothing, circuit stability, and the necessary rejection at the switching frequency.

Because the primary interest of this study is the effect of the switching regulator on the input power line, only the rectifier, input filter, and the dc to dc converter are investigated. The study included measurements of various rectifier and filter combinations as well as the development of several computer models. In this regard, both forward and backward models were investigated. In both the measurement and forward modeling phases, detailed knowledge of the circuit elements is required. Although this requirement makes forward modeling less useful in EMI analysis, such models nevertheless serve to provide an understanding of the device. In the backward-looking model the nonlinear source is replaced by an equivalent current source with the appropriate harmonic structure. This approach is ideal for EMI analysis because the general characteristics of the switching source are known and can be easily computed. Thus, an EMI model can be constructed that computes the effects of the nonlinear switching power supply without a knowledge of the circuit elements in a specific supply.

COMPUTER MODEL

A new computer program, POWSUP, has been written to predict CE01 and CE03 conducted emissions from switching power supplies. This program is an outgrowth of a program originally written in 1976 to predict total harmonic voltage distortion from nonlinear loads on three-phase power buses^[2]. Similar to its predecessor, POWSUP is an interactive program that asks the user for the various parameters

of the power system to be modeled. Output is returned to the screen where the user can observe the voltages and currents in various locations on the power bus. The total harmonic distortion (THD) is then computed for the range of frequencies specified and for each load in the model. If switching power supplies have been specified as the load, the CE03 currents returned to the generator are also shown. At the end of each model the user is given the option of running another case. Figure 3 is a flow diagram for the computer program.

POWSUP is divided into a CE01 and a CE03 section. The program can calculate harmonic voltages given the configuration of a shipboard powerline. These voltages can be used to predict the THD expected at various locations on the power bus. Harmonic distortion can subject susceptible equipment to voltages that will cause degraded operation. The CS01 specification of MIL-STD-461C^[3] provides the level of voltage required on input power lines to cause degraded operation of susceptible equipment. With this information, the ship designer can identify potential problem areas before the equipment is actually installed on a platform.

THE CE01 MODEL

The computer program models a balanced three-phase wye-wye or delta-delta power distribution system as a single-phase circuit. Harmonic distortion caused by nonlinear loads is modeled by ideal current sources shunting the load impedance. These current sources can be given assumed harmonic structures that match measured data. The model can

Figure 3. Flow Diagram for Power Supply (POWSUP) Computer Program

analyze up to 10 balanced loads fed in parallel from the generator. Harmonic voltages and currents are computed at various points in the power distribution system, and the total harmonic distortion is estimated as a figure of merit for the particular configuration. The model can accommodate a 60 Hz or 400 Hz generator.

Figure 4(a) shows a typical delta power distribution system and figure 4(b) shows the equivalent wye distribution system. If the systems are balanced then we can write the delta system in its equivalent wye formulation as

$$Z_{an} = \frac{Z_{ab}}{3},$$

$$|I_{an}| = \sqrt{3} |I_{ab}|,$$

and

$$|V_{ab}| = \sqrt{3} |V_{an}|.$$

Figure 4(a). Delta:Delta Power Distribution System

Figure 4(b). Equivalent Wye:Wye Power Distribution System

Each representation has an equivalent formulation for the total power. The total power transferred to the load for the wye distribution is

$$P = 3 |V_{an}| |I_{an}| P_f \tag{1}$$

The power factor, P_f , is assumed to be unity. By substitution of the equivalent V and I in equation 1, the total power transferred to the load in the equivalent delta system can be found. Once the wye formulation has been determined, we need only analyze one leg of the circuit to determine the voltages and currents for the system. Figure 4(c) shows the wye system reduced to one leg.

Figure 5 shows one leg of a power distribution system that has N nonlinear loads in parallel. In order to predict the harmonic distortion due to these loads, the nonlinear loads are replaced by linear current sources whose properties are determined from

$$R = \frac{V_{ab}^2}{P_0} \quad \text{line-to-neutral}$$

and

$$I_1 = \frac{P_0}{3V_{ab}} \quad \text{line-to-line-current.}$$

Figure 4(c). One Leg of the Wye Power Distribution System

Figure 4. Power System Configuration, Where Z_g Is Generated Impedance, Z_t Is Transmission Line Impedance, Z_L Is Load Impedance, and I_n Is the Amplitude of the n th Harmonic

Z_g = GENERATOR IMPEDANCE
 Z_t = TRANSMISSION LINE IMPEDANCE
 Z_b = BRANCH LINE IMPEDANCE
 Z_L = LOAD IMPEDANCE

Figure 5. One Leg of a Power Distribution System With m Nonlinear Loads in Parallel

The spectral properties of the current source can be specified as having the following characteristics: $1/n$, $1/n^{1.5}$, $1/n^2$, or 3 percent of the fundamental, or capacitively coupled model. These correspond to fall-off rates of -20 dB/dec, -30 dB/dec, -40 dB/dec, and 0 dB/dec, respectively. The capacitively coupled model represents a flat spectrum to the 13th harmonic and then a fall off of -60 dB/dec. The $1/n$ model represents the inductive filter model where the inductance is very much greater than the critical inductance^[4]. The other models refer to fall-off rates that have been observed experimentally. The 3 percent model is the limit imposed by MIL-STD-461C.

For any source, the amplitude of a given harmonic can be determined from

$$I_n = I_1 SF \frac{1}{n^m}$$

where

n = number of the harmonic,

m = slope of the fall-off rate,

SF = scale factor = 1,

I_1 = amplitude of the fundamental,

and I_n = amplitude of the n th harmonic.

The scale factor parameter allows the flat spectrum model to be implemented. For the 3 percent model, SF=.03 and $m = 1$. In fact, any flat spectrum model could be implemented with this parameter.

One of the techniques to reduce the amplitude of the low frequency rectifier harmonics is to use multi-phase power supplies. In our model we have assumed that the power system is a balanced three-phase delta connected system. A three-phase full wave rectifier has a pulse rate of 6. This means that the harmonics are related by $6n \pm 1$. Power supplies having higher pulse rates will shift the harmonic frequencies by multiples of six. For example, the first harmonic for a 24-pulse system would be the 23rd. Additional harmonics would be generated according to $24n \pm 1$, for $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. Note that $1/23 \approx 0.04$ is very close to the 3 percent harmonic current limit required by military specification [3]. With the technology already available to implement this technique, it is necessary to analyze nonlinear loads that have pulse rates greater than six.

To compute the harmonic voltages at each load and at the point generator output (see figure 6), the current that returns to the generator from each source must be known. To compute the current, the total admittance of the circuit must be calculated. The following analytical procedure shows how the harmonic voltages and currents are computed.

The variables for each branch at each harmonic frequency are defined as

- V_{go} = Voltage at the point generator output
- Y_g = Admittance of the generator and transmission line
- A_m = Ratio of the current returning to the generator from the m^{th} branch to the total current of the m^{th} branch or the total admittance of the network as seen from the m^{th} branch
- $I_m(f)$ = Source strength of m^{th} branch at frequency f
- Y_{rcm} = Admittance of rc network of the m^{th} branch
- Y_r = Sum of the admittance of the branches, excluding the m^{th} branch
- Z_{Lm} = Impedance of the m^{th} load
- Y_m = Admittance of the m^{th} branch
- Z_{bm} = Impedance of the m^{th} branch of the power cable
- C_m = Capacitance of m^{th} branch
- R_m = Resistance of the m^{th} load
- R_{bm} = Resistance of the m^{th} branch of the power cable
- L_{bm} = Inductance of the m^{th} branch of the power cable
- Z_g = Generator impedance
- Z_t = Transmission line impedance
- R_g = Generator resistance
- L_g = Line-neutral inductance of generator
- R_t = Transmission line resistance
- L_t = Transmission line inductance
- V_m = Voltage of the m^{th} load

The voltage at the point generator output (see figure 6) is

$$V_{go}(f) = \frac{I_t(f)}{Y_g(f)},$$

where

$$I_t(f) = \sum_{m=1}^M A_m(f) I_m(f),$$

is the total current that returns to the generator of frequency f and

$$A_m = \frac{Y_g(f)}{Y_{rcm}(f) + Y_r(f) + Y_g(f) + Y_{rcm} Z_{bm} \{Y_r + Y_g\}}$$

is the total admittance of the network as seen from the m^{th} branch. The various individual admittances are given by,

$$Y_r = \sum_{m=1}^M \lambda_{mr} Y_m(f), \quad \lambda_{mr} = \begin{cases} 1 & m \neq r \\ 0 & m = r \end{cases}$$

$$Y_m(f) = \frac{Y_{rcm}(f)}{Z_{bm}(f) Y_{rcm}(f) + 1},$$

$$Y_{rcm} = \frac{j\omega C_m R_m + 1}{R_m}$$

The impedance of the m^{th} branch Z_{bm} (see figure 6) is given by,

$$Z_{bm} = R_{bm} + j\omega L_{bm}$$

The admittance of the generator is

$$Y_g = \frac{1}{Z_g + Z_t},$$

where

$$Z_g = R_g + j\omega L_g$$

and

$$Z_t = R_t + j\omega L_t.$$

Finally, the voltage at the m^{th} load can be found from

$$V_m = Z_{bm} I_n \sqrt{3} + V_{go}.$$

This is an approximation of the true voltage, as shown in figure 6. The nonlinear load could easily have been represented with the current source in series with the load; in this case, the equation for the voltage would be exact. Therefore, as a first approximation, it is assumed that the voltage distortion at the load depends only on the voltage drop on the branch connected to that load, plus the voltage distortion due to the harmonic currents returning to the generator. Note that in this particular model, R_{bm} , R_t , and R_g are assumed to have zero line resistance, which is a good approximation for low frequency harmonics.

Figure 6. One Leg of a Power Distribution System With m Nonlinear Loads Replaced by m Linear Current Sources

The THD is computed using an approximation of its standard definition by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) [5]. Thus, for a three-phase nonlinear source, the THD is

$$THD \approx \frac{(V_5^2 + V_7^2 + V_{11}^2 + V_{13}^2)^{1/2}}{V_1} 100 + 1\%$$

where V_1 is the rms voltage at the fundamental. The 1 percent is added to account for the harmonic voltage distortion attributable to the generator.

In summary the CEO1 model includes multi-phase power supplies, up to 100 harmonics of the fundamental for a six-pulse rectifier (the number of harmonics for higher pulse numbers is determined from $\frac{600}{P}$ where P is the number of pulses), choice of five harmonic fall-off models, including a model for capacitively coupled power supplies, computation of CEO1 conducted emissions currents that return to the generator at each harmonic, computation of THD for all harmonics, error trap routines, and the ability to cycle through the program to run multiple cases.

CEO3 EMISSION MODEL

The model for switching power supplies replaces the nonlinear load with a linear current source having spectral characteristics similar to the load it is replacing. The CEO3 current source would be in parallel with the CEO1 source and would have infinite impedance. This is necessary to prevent current from the CEO1 source from seeing an additional branch. The new current source would replace the smoothing filter as well as the switching circuits. This is all that is necessary to model because most switching regulators are transformer coupled for dc-dc isolation. The impedance of this second source would effectively be the resistive component computed from the output power, or

$$R = \frac{V_{ab}^2}{P_o}$$

The characteristics of the smoothing filter are taken into account in the computation of the amplitudes of the harmonics for this source.

The characteristics of the CEO3 current source can be found by assuming a worst-case model first introduced by Kamm [6, 7] in 1978. Figure 7 shows a simplified model of the worst-case switching topology, which is the Buck converter. Here the two-pole switch represents the switching transistor that turns the input current on and off, resulting in a square wave on the input side of the device. The diode maintains current in the load while the switch is off. However, the switching transistor has a finite rise and fall time; typical switching transistor rise times are on the order of 100 ns.

Figure 7. Simple Model of Switching Power Supply, Using Buck Topology

Thus, in this model, the switching source is replaced by a symmetrical trapezoidal periodic waveform. Figure 8(a) shows the waveform for the proposed current source. The normalized Fourier coefficients for an infinite train of symmetrical trapezoidal pulses are

$$C_n = \frac{2}{(n\pi)^2} ft_r \sin[n\pi f(t_o + t_r)] \sin(n\pi f t_r),$$

where the constants are defined in figure 8(a).

Figure 8(a). Trapezoidal Wave with period T = 50 μsec, rise time t_r = 30 nsec, and duty cycle t_o = 25 μsec

In order to more accurately model the waveshape of the switching current, the turn-on spike of the diode recovery current can also be included. The diode recovery spike is modeled as a pulsed, critically damped, exponentially decaying sine wave. Because the total waveform is the summation of two independent effects, the waveforms can be analyzed separately in the frequency domain. Figure 8(b) shows the waveform of the pulsed exponentially decaying sine wave and is represented by,

$$f(t) = e^{-\alpha t} \sin bt$$

where

α = damping factor

$b = 2\pi f_0$, and

f_0 = frequency of the sine wave.

The Fourier coefficients for the waveform shown in figure 8(b) can be found by integrating $f(t)$ over the period by

$$C_n = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T f(t) e^{-j2\pi n t f} dt$$

Figure 8(b). Pulsed Exponentially Decaying Sine Wave where T = 50 μsec, f_0 = 3 MHz $\alpha = 1.153 \times 10^5$ and t = 50 μsec

The integration gives the normalized coefficients as

$$C_n = \frac{1}{2jT} \left(\frac{e^{z_2 t} - 1}{z_2} - \frac{e^{-z_1 t} - 1}{z_1} \right)$$

where

$$z_1 = \alpha - j(b - 2n\pi f_0)$$

and

$$z_2 = \alpha + j(b + 2n\pi f_0)$$

The combined waveform for the trapezoidal switching current with diode recovery spike is shown in figure 9. The resultant Fourier transform is also shown in this figure. This plot is for a switching frequency of 20 kHz, rise time of 30 ns, and a 1 amp turn-on spike. This curve serves as the basis for our model. Kamm^[6] gives the characteristics of an idealized smoothing filter, and this filter has been implemented into the model to compute the estimated amplitudes of the CE03 current source. Figure 10 shows the characteristics of this filter, and figure 11 shows the estimated amplitude of a 1 amp switching source at 20 kHz reflected through the smoothing filter. These estimates agree very well with those shown in reference 6 for similar waveforms. Note that in this new model, switching frequencies up to ≈ 100 kHz are allowed. For switching currents greater than 1 amp, the amplitudes can be scaled by,

$$R_X = 20 \text{ Log}(I_1).$$

Figure 9. Fourier Coefficients for 20-kHz Trapezoidal Wave With Diode Recovery Spike

Figure 10. Idealized Smoothing Filter

Figure 11. Estimated Amplitude of Switching Source Model at 20-kHz Reflected Through Smoothing Filter. Also shown is the CE03 limit line for a 60 Hz load current $\leq 1A$ narrow band. Note that the CE03 limit line is not shown above 1 MHz.

SAMPLE POWER SUPPLY RUNS

In this section, sample runs are used to illustrate the capability of the computer model using a hypothetical power distribution system. Total harmonic distortion and return currents are computed for various pulse rate systems. The computer model is also compared to shipboard measurements taken on a 43.2-kW motor generator, 400-Hz power distribution system. Measured and computed THD are shown for various loads on the power distribution system.

Hypothetical Power Supply Runs

Because the low frequency conducted emissions dominate harmonic distortion on the power bus, the effect of using multiphase power supplies will be the first example shown. Figure 12 shows a 135-kW, 400-Hz power distribution system with six nonlinear loads. Table 1 compares the THD at the point generator output for various multiphase supplies; all the sources are assumed to have a 1/n fall off, 0° firing angle, and instantaneous commutation.

Figure 12. Hypothetical Powerline Configuration

Clearly, as the pulse number increases, the THD decreases. In fact, for 18-pulse supplies, the THD is almost 5 percent, which is the limit for voltage distortion, and for 24-pulse supplies, the THD is below the limit. However, the real problem with harmonic current is not the type of distortion, but the magnitude of current flowing at the various frequencies back to the generator. Table 2 shows the current that returns to the generator for the various pulse numbers. Note the particularly high currents that are flowing in the VLF range. If these currents are allowed to flow on the structure through line-to-ground filters, large magnetic fields, which could interfere with sensitive equipment or low level signal transmission lines, would be generated. Structure currents are known to be a significant problem, particularly in the VLF range.

Table 1. Comparison of Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) (THD) at Point Generator Output for Multiphase Supplies

Pulse No.	THD (%)
6	8.5
12	6.4
18	5.1
24	4.3

Table 2. Predicted CE01 Currents Returning to Generator for Various Pulse Numbers

Frequency (Hz)	Current (A)			
	6 PULSE	12 PULSE	18 PULSE	24 PULSE
2000	41.8			
2800	27.8			
4400	15.0	15.0		
5200	11.6	11.6		
6800	7.5		7.5	
7600	6.2		6.2	
9200	4.4	4.4		4.4
10000	3.8	3.8		3.8
14000	2.4		2.4	
14800	1.8		1.8	
18800	1.2	1.2		1.2
19600	1.1	1.1		1.1

Shipboard Run

As a final study, shipboard data will be compared with predicted data; figure 13 shows the power distribution system for the shipboard data. In this experiment, the THD was measured for various loads on the 400-Hz, 43.2-kW power distribution system. An attempt was made to model the various sources with the appropriate fall off; however, often the measured harmonic fall off was between the models available. In those cases, the model that provided the best fit was chosen. Line-to-ground capacitance was included when the data were available. Table 3 summarizes the measured data, comparing the predicted THD with measured values. All loads were six-pulse sources. The data shown in the table, although by no means exact, are close enough to indicate that the chosen model is a good first attempt at predicting the expected THD. Table 4 shows the expected currents that return to the generator from these loads. These data were computed under the same conditions as those in table 3. The currents shown in table 4 are by no means insignificant; if allowed to flow through the structure, they would cause considerable interference. One way to control the propagation of such structure currents is to provide isolation for all nonlinear equipments. Although this works well in controlling structure currents, the extra weight and expense to provide this isolation are prohibitive.

Table 3. Comparison of Measured and Predicted Values of Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) from the Shipboard Data

Load	Measured THD (%)	Predicted THD (%)	Model No.
1	3.3	5.00	2
2	3.4	5.01	2
3	4.2	5.02	2
4	3.54	5.02	2
5	3.76	4.99	2
6	4.39	5.15	2
7	3.94	5.14	2

Figure 13. Model of the 43.2-kW, 400-Hz shipboard power Distribution System

Table 4. Predicted Emission Currents Returning to Generator From the Shipboard Data

Frequency (Hz)	Current (A)
2000	7.0
2800	3.9
4400	1.6
5200	1.1

CONCLUSIONS

Harmonic distortion models for switching power supplies were investigated for 60 Hz to 50 MHz frequency range. A computer program has been developed to incorporate both low CE01 and high CE03 frequency sources. It computes conducted emission currents that return to the generator in both frequency ranges for various nonlinear loads. These loads can be arranged in any way desired, can have various pulse rates, and can utilize dissipative or switching power supplies. The results have been shown to agree well with actual measurements from shipboard power distribution systems. The program can be used as an effective design tool for predicting the worst-case level of harmonic distortion from nonlinear loads on proposed power distribution systems. Such data are invaluable to the design engineer who needs familiarity with the effects of nonlinear high power loads on a power distribution system, but does not need an extensive knowledge of each load.

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